

→ Why the Electric Universe isn't the same as the Plasma Universe and why it matters: Part I (Sep2018)

MESS 0005

The Sun is Electric - it is an “Electric Sun” - Period.

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September 2022

ABSTRACT

Critics of the Electric Universe love to split hairs and claim it is a cult. There are plenty in the Plasma Universe that wish to distance themselves, professionally and personally, from the EU as if it is a form of “flat Earth.” This is a ridiculous psyop perpetrated by the mainstream to get people to not question the Peer Review Cult¹. In point of fact, the issues are getting down to the level of minor philosophical differences. The Sun being electric *is not one of them* because this is an objective, empirical fact, and it has nothing to do with the opinions of tiny, ego-charged humans. **The sun is electric and it is an Electric Sun.**

Keywords: Solar Physics - fusion - electric fields - MHD - Juergens - Alfven - Scott - Samuel

¹

https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

Re: “Plasma Universe is *different* than Electric Universe”

Mr. Johnson has put forward, within the first 10 minutes some very salient critiques of the “Electric Universe” - or rather the Thunderbolts Project © - which are pedantic, hair-splitting, full of weasel words (eg “they never miss a chance to remind you...”), and some of which the author himself has stated in a comparison of EU vs. EPEMC². Nevertheless, the main issue of this presentation *outside* of the obvious biases, is that **all plasma cosmology** whether it is that of K. Birkeland (1905), I. Langmuir (1927), or A. Peratt (1992)³ is based on **classical electromagnetism**. The aethereal mechanics of R. Distinti⁴ is based upon *New* Electromagnetism⁵, otherwise it is presumed that all other work is a Maxwell-Heaviside-Tesla-Steinmetzian flavor missing the contexts of Weber⁶ and Alfven or even Feynman et al. Nevertheless, that does not mean that P.U. is wrong. But to imply that Peratt is the father of P.U. is completely ridiculous.

Stars - like all other things - cannot perform work on themselves⁷. Gravity-based fusion cannot generate both fusion and plasma material in order to generate electric fields and *that is the salient point*. The Sun is electric because it requires electricity to function, produces electric fields, and creates fused material in the coronasphere from Farnsworth-type fusion⁸ processes, which are replicated in SAFIRE⁹ lab! The Sun is electric because:

- It has an electric field¹⁰
- This field accelerates charged particles¹¹
- This field cannot be magnetism alone^{12 13}
- Charges are in motion and generating magnetic fields¹⁴

Re: “the Plasma Universe does not say the sun is electric”

More to the point it is *an Electric Sun*, and part of an *Electric Sky* (*via* interacting with our “Plasma-electromagnetic Sky”), precisely because it is electric and it **runs on giant electrical filaments**¹⁵ and is part of a certain scale of electromagnetic filamentary circuit¹⁶, governed of course by Kirchoff’s circuitry and the concepts within force-free aligned fields (Birkeland Currents via a Bessel Function¹⁷), which are counter-rotating, coaxial field¹⁸s where electricity is leading magnetism by 90 degrees phase in parallel.

These are not facts up for dispute, they are matters of empirical observation.

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https://www.academia.edu/73271902/Paradigm_Shift_Comparison_EPEMC_vs_The_Rest_Comparing_PEMC_EU_PU_MU_and_SM_BSM

³ [peratt-plasma-cosmology.pdf](#)

⁴ www.distinti.com

⁵ <http://www.distinti.com/docs/neThesis.pdf>

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/weber>

⁷ What is the 1st Law of Thermodynamics? The First Law Explained!

⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Philo-Farnsworth>

⁹ [safire-project-1.pdf](#)

¹⁰ <https://now.iowa.edu/2021/07/physicists-led-university-iowa-more-fully-describe-suns-electric-field>

¹¹ http://sdpha2.ucsd.edu/Solar/pdf_Solar/agu20_cfd_Electric_Magnetic_All_v4.pdf

¹² <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/2006RG000195>

¹³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7380306/>

¹⁴ <https://www.nde-ed.org/Physics/Magnetism/fieldcreation.xhtml>

¹⁵ http://www.esa.int/spaceinimages/Images/2018/03/Chaotic_web_of_filaments_in_a_Milky_Way_stellar_nursery

¹⁶ The Local Chimney

¹⁷ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>

¹⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

❖ “Remember, if it disagrees with experiment, it’s wrong.” ~Feynman

The simple fact is that the sun is electric because >>It is an Electric Sun<<. Electricity is not caused by gravity as NASA falsely stated in 2021 (50 years late to the party that Alfvén and Juergens started). That’s Bass Ackwards¹⁹, the gravity is the result of the remainder of complex subtractions involving charged masses rearranging in a homeostatic bubble, probably dual-layered condensed plasma or ultra hot crystalline plasma (though the core is definitely cold²⁰). Fused materials are the remnants of typical forced and unforced transmutations at both high *charged* pressures, and at low, even ‘dark mode’ or ‘vacuum’ pressures which draw in material from the Void or counter space (confirmed Schwinger Effect, 2022). The pinch which begins a star is either a Herbig Haro event or the result of Marklund convection, either way our sun sits within the Local Chimney and rotates with other stars through the Galactic Electric Circuit.

★ SGEN → GEC → SSEC → **the Sun** → PEC → PEMS²¹ → HEGEME → Life on Earth

Scales vary from 10^{18} to 10^{12} to 10^{11} - 10^9 to 10^6 to 10^3 to 10^5 - 10^6 , respectively²², in amps or volts, depending on the object of observation.

Re: This is my sandbox and you’re not invited *kick*

While not technically POS behavior²³, there is a strong (and disappointing) behavior in the altstream that is the result of the *beta-male* facsimile effect. In essence, because the mainstream has the “on the bus”²⁴ alpha (so to speak) ability to bully anyone it wants, and push anyone out - even if they are mainstream, too (like Halton Arp) - as well as ruin their lives and reputations, with impunity. The beta males want this power, so they do something similar but more pathetic (if that is possible). They form little islands, little sandboxes, where they have built a very fragile ecosystem - a sandcastle - around their ideas, and then kick sand in the faces of anyone that approaches, even if they could play in the sandbox. Even if they agree 99%, it’s almost as if they are “too similar.” Wheeler-Distinti, LaPointe-Dollard, Peratt-Thornhill, etc.

It’s a little sad when one or both parties kick sand in the others’ faces, and that appears to be what B. Johnson is doing in this presentation. It isn’t that it isn’t important to differentiate. G. Samuel made several videos talking about the differences between the Electric Universe and Plasma Cosmology, however he isn’t kicking sand in anyone’s eyes and has no “dog in the fight” (though he has been on Thunderbolts Project several times). He does the job *professionally*, without insinuating there are issues with Peratt or with Thornhill that have anything to do with something other than their professional opinions. That’s why after these videos, he was still invited onto the “Thunderbolts Project” YouTube channel. No professional bias. As such we are going to share a litany of his videos on this subject and the electric sun topic, as well as a series of SAFIRE videos so the audience can judge for themselves.

¹⁹ Above: rare NASA fish

²⁰ See: spectra of sunspots

²¹

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

²² https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis p.10

²³ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

²⁴ My God Michael Shermer is such a P.O.S.

Table 1 - Electric and Plasma Universe, See the Pattern & SAFIRE

<i>The Electric Sun</i>	<i>Plasma²⁵ Cosmology vs. EU</i>	<i>SAFIRE</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Juergens' Electric Sun - P... ▶ The Electric Solar Enviro... ▶ The Red Square Nebula ... ▶ Beyond Juergens Electric... ▶ How do Stars and Giant ... https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EuLOYUxZVz0²⁶ ▶ Are We Witnessing the Bi... ▶ 5 Reasons the Sun's Fusi... ▶ Overcoming the Fusion li... ▶ Why do Astronomers cont... ▶ The Birth and Death of an... ▶ UNEXPLAINED Problem... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Plasma Universe & Electr... ▶ Plasma Universe - The U... ▶ Plasma Universe Model ... ▶ Does Plasma Produce a ... ▶ A Universe without Dark ... ▶ The Local Void Mystery P... ▶ A Galaxy's AGN Switched... ▶ Interstellar Clouds and th... ▶ Scientist Discover Cosmi... ▶ Galaxy so Large it should... ▶ Understanding Double La... ▶ Understanding Double La... ▶ Understanding Double La... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ SAFIRE: A Real-World Te... ▶ Michael Clarage: SAFIRE... ▶ Montgomery Childs: SAFI... ▶ SAFIRE Phase 2 Dr. Mic... ▶ Special Feature: THE SA... ▶ The SAFIRE Project 201... ▶ The SAFIRE Project - Th... ▶ The SAFIRE PROJECT 2... ▶ Special Feature: SAFIRE ... ▶ Interview with Monty Chil... ▶ Origin of the Safire Sun ▶ Cosmic Plasma & Safire ... ▶ My REACTION to the SA...

Summary

The Sun is electric **and** it is an Electric Sun - people should stop playing word games. There is no doubt on this at this point, there is only the doubt as to how much X:Y:Z the current comes from the GEC, how much from the SSEC (as recycling), and how much from the Counterspace²⁷, now that we know the Schwinger Effect²⁸ is confirmed²⁹ and the SAFIRE “Dark mode” effect of 7% input, 100% output is also confirmed. According to the fractal Universe theory, the ratio will have something to do with phi, e, tau (2pi), or something similar.

But the useful facts are as summarized:

- ▶ The sun is electric
- ▶ It is an Electric Sun
- ▶ Plasma is electric
- ▶ Electric Fields are not created by gravity
- ▶ Gravity is weak compared to electricity (10⁻³⁷ weaker)
- ▶ Gasses don't perform work on themselves
- ▶ The Universe is full of SGEC and GEC filaments
- ▶ The Sun is on a filament called the Local Chimney

²⁵ ▶ Understanding Bennett Pinches and Z-Pinches in 60 Seconds < Plasma Cosmology Glossary Playlist!

²⁶ Why is it that only Wal Thornhill's video won't autosuggest a replacement icon? Shadowbanning?

²⁷ https://www.academia.edu/63382042/ Something_from_Nothing ie- the spongy counter space (SCS)

²⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1106.5965>

²⁹ <https://bgr.com/science/scientists-create-matter-from-nothing-in-groundbreaking-experiment/>

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